

Heat treatment of medium carbon steel: Acoustic and mechanical characterization

Jorge Vera Alvarado¹; Luis Caballero García²; Martín Taboada Neira³; Junior Hidalgo Ruiz⁴; Junior Sánchez Sánchez⁵
Universidad Nacional de Trujillo, Perú

Heat treatments are planned based on the pre-established mechanical requirements for an industrial component. The mechanical characterization of a component in service using conventional tests is not feasible due to its destructive nature, therefore, it is necessary to explore an alternative non-destructive method that allows predicting the mechanical properties of a material without affecting its service condition. The mechanical properties of a metal alloy have an intrinsic relationship with the microstructural characteristics, as well as with the acoustic properties of the material. For this reason, the objective of this research work was to obtain a quantitative relationship between acoustic and mechanical measurements for medium carbon steel subjected to heat treatments of quenching and tempering. For this purpose, nine experimental runs were planned by factorial interaction of the austenization temperature of 850, 900, and 950°C, and the tempering temperature of 25 (without tempering), 550, and 650°C. The samples were characterized by optical metallography, Vickers hardness, and ultrasound with longitudinal waves. The microstructural changes in the samples according to the imposed thermal cycle reported results that demonstrate a significant difference in the measurements of hardness, speed, and acoustic attenuation according to statistical tests. The experimental reports indicate a gradual decrease in hardness as the tempering temperature increases due to a greater presence of tempered martensite. The speed and acoustic attenuation measurements gradually decrease to a minimum value as hardness increases up to a maximum value obtained in the samples tempered without tempering; consequently, there is greater resistance to the propagation of the ultrasonic beam. Acoustic and mechanical correlations are presented as a non-destructive alternative for hardness characterization.

Keywords: Heat treatment, Quenching, Tempering, Medium carbon steel.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15880562

¹ Master in Materials Science and Technology and PhD in Environmental Sciences. Contact: jvera@unitru.edu.pe

² Metallurgical Engineer. Contact: lcaballerog@unitru.pe

³ Metallurgical Engineer and Doctor in Environmental Sciences. Contact: mtaboada@unitru.edu.pe

⁴ Metallurgical Engineer. Contact: jhidalgor@unitru.edu.pe

⁵ Metallurgical Engineer. Contact: jsanchezs@unitru.edu.pe

1. INTRODUCTION

Ferrous alloys are in high demand in the industrial sector due to their great versatility in mechanical properties and their sensitivity to variations in the function of the microstructural constituents, a product of the thermal cycle imposed during heat treatments. However, in service, repair, maintenance, or both conditions, they are also sensitive to suffer some alteration in their properties, generally due to thermal effects. Characterizing the material in real time using conventional methods is not feasible due to its destructive nature, as it exposes it to a high risk of failure [1]. The search for alternative non-destructive methods for the mechanical characterization of a material without harming its service condition is one of the most pressing needs in the industry.

The non-destructive ultrasonic testing method developed to detect defects in metallic structures is a technological alternative to explore due to the dependent relationship between the internal structure of a material and the acoustic impedance susceptible to experimental measurements [2]. In addition, there is a direct relationship between the speed of propagation of the ultrasonic wave with the density and elastic modulus of a crystalline material [3]. Such conditions are promising for monitoring a crystalline material modified microstructurally by thermal effects through experimental measurements of the acoustic properties. In addition, various studies have demonstrated its usefulness in the characterization and life cycle evaluation of structural components in service [4-7]. The mechanical and acoustic responses of a material are associated with its internal and structural characteristics [6, 8].

The internal structure of a metallic material, due to its diverse shapes, sizes, crystalline structure, and orientation, influences the measurements of its elastic and acoustic properties in a material [6, 9]. The elastic modulus of a material has a linear relationship with the speed of propagation of the ultrasonic beam within the structure in which it propagates. It is also indicated that the higher the density of dislocations and the degree of distortion of the network in the crystal lattice, the greater the resistance to the propagation of the ultrasonic beam in the material, affecting the acoustic impedance measurements [10, 11]. Consequently, experimental characterization is possible through easily measured acoustic parameters [12, 13].

Various modern technologies aimed at material characterization using ultrasonic methods have been constantly evolving. Acoustoelasticity methods for determining residual stresses in additively manufactured products require electromagnetic-acoustic (EMA) and piezoelectric (PEP) transducers [14]. Furthermore, multiple shadowing methods with Rayleigh waves and EMA are used to monitor surface and near-surface defects in small-diameter pipes [15]. Furthermore, head and surface waves are applied to reveal near-surface cracks [16], and plate and head waves are used to characterize elastic anisotropy [17].

The acoustoelastic method compared to the conventional method by contact of the transducer to the test element, provides greater precision in acoustic measurements. On the other hand, EMA converters have a low conversion coefficient, which is why there is a need to develop special equipment for processing acoustic signals without contact [18]. In addition, to implement this test system turns out to be more expensive and complex to provide in situ coverage to a component in service concerning conventional contact methods. The methods for conventional acoustic characterization with piezoelectric contact transducers impose higher requirements for measurement accuracy.

The works developed in materials have demonstrated their effectiveness for acoustic characterization, the recommendations are greater dimensional control in the samples, ensuring flatness in the sample, and a stable contact between the translator and the contact surface.

The attenuation of ultrasonic waves in polycrystalline materials occurs mainly by scattering at the structural boundaries between grains or by absorption of acoustic energy, produced due to the damping generated by dislocations in the structure, by thermoelastic losses and by magnetic hysteresis, or both [19-21]. Various investigations attribute the greatest energy losses to be produced by scattering of the ultrasonic beam at the structural boundaries [22-24], increasing the level of attenuation in structures with larger grain size and as the wavelength of the ultrasonic beam decreases [1]. The three scattering regimes established in the acoustic theory are divided based on the relationship between the average grain size in structure D and the

wavelength of the ultrasonic beam λ , as detailed in [25]. The regimes are the Rayleigh region $\lambda \gg D$, the stochastic region $\lambda \approx D$ and the geometric region $\lambda < D$.

Ferrous alloys are characterized and distinguished from others because their microstructure is modified by heat treatments and important changes are conferred on the material in its mechanical properties. The phase transformations imposed from the austenisation region to room temperature produce microstructural constituents that are sensitive to variation by interaction with the ultrasonic beam and therefore to be characterized by acoustic measurements. A substructure that tenses the network or interrupts the continuity of the matrix reduces the speed at which the ultrasonic beam propagates by reducing the elastic modulus.

Furthermore, in carbon steels, it has been shown that both the attenuation coefficient and the ultrasonic wave velocity increase gradually as the phase transformations occur from the austenitic region by cooling to room temperature in the following structural order: 1) Martensite, 2) Bainite, 3) Fine pearlite, 4) Coarse pearlitic, and 5) Ferrite. Likewise, the separation distance between ferrite and cementite layers in the pearlitic constituents influences the magnitude of the acoustic measurements [26].

Heat treatments are controlled processes of heating/cooling cycles that produce microstructural changes in steels, therefore, modifying the mechanical properties of the material, such as hardness, tensile strength, impact toughness, ductility, and corrosion resistance, among others [27]. The tempering heat treatment in steels occurs by heating the sample to a temperature above the upper critical temperature in the Fe - Fe₃C meta-stable diagram until a complete austenitic transformation, followed by rapid cooling to room temperature, to produce martensitic transformation in the steel. Tempering is widely used to increase hardness and strength in blades, shafts, gears, and structural components [28].

The tempering heat treatment is carried out after quenching by heating below the lower critical temperature in the Fe - Fe₃C meta-stable diagram followed by slow cooling. During tempering, a transformation of the martensitic structure into tempered martensite occurs. Tempering at high temperatures decreases the hardness compared to its initial tempered condition [28].

Characterizing a component by conventional mechanical testing due to its destructive nature requires additional costs for the preparation and safeguarding of test specimens. Ultrasonic testing by the pulse-echo technique, due to its non-destructive nature, speed, and precision of testing, is presented as a promising technological alternative to explore for use in industrial applications. Therefore, the objective of the research was to obtain a correlation between the resistance to indentation and the acoustic parameters obtained in medium carbon steel subjected to heat treatments of quenching and tempering. The results of the correlation of hardness with acoustic measurements by the industrial ultrasound testing method are intended for the mechanical prediction of a metallic component with similar metallurgical characteristics.

2. METHOD

2.1 Material object of study

For the experimental execution in the present research work, a medium carbon mechanical construction steel under the designation AISI 1045 widely used in the industrial sector was selected. The chemical composition reported in the delivery state by the manufacturer is characterized by having 0.435% C, 0.640% Mn, 0.33% Si, 0.03% P and 0.03% S. Each sample of 30 mm in diameter was prepared by mechanical cutting according to the scheme shown in Figure 1. The dimensional finish with an accuracy of 0.001 mm was carried out by mechanical cutting, roughing, and polishing, the flatness and parallelism between the surface of both parallel faces in the sample was carefully ensured.

Figure 1. Study sample geometry

2.2 Methods and Techniques

The experimental runs, variables, and factors for each treatment are detailed in Table 1. The heating of the specimens was carried out in a muffle-type electric resistance furnace with automatic temperature control. The temperature range for austenitization in the samples for the tempering heat treatment and the 60-minute holding time were planned based on the transformation curve by continuous cooling of AISI 1045 steel [29]. The tempering temperatures were selected based on the manufacturer's recommendations.

Table 1. Study variables

Austenitization temperature (°C)	Cooling medium	Tempering temperature (°C)	Cooling medium
850	Water	25	Air
900	Water	550	Air
950	Water	650	Air

Metallographic tests for microstructural characterization were performed following the sequence of surface preparation by rough grinding and mechanical polishing with diamond paste up to 3.0 μm , for chemical attack with 2% Nital. Microstructural details were observed with a ZEISS AXIO optical metallographic microscope, model Vert.A1.

The resistance tests were carried out using indentation hardness measurements with an Innovatest Falcon 500 brand test equipment on the Vickers scale, in particular following the recommendations of the ASTM E384 standard.

The ultrasound test for acoustic characterization of each sample was performed using the pulse-echo technique with an industrial ultrasound device, Krautkramer brand, model USM 36, from General Electric, by the recommendations established in reference standards ASTM E 494-20 and ASTM E 664. The calibration and qualification requirement of the equipment was verified with a 5 MHz frequency transducer by AWS D1.1. The measurement error based on 10 measurements on the same point on a reference standard is not greater than 0.05%.

The longitudinal beam ultrasonic wave propagation velocity measurements V (m/s) are calculated according to Equation (1), and according to the recommendation established in [30]. The travel distance X (m) and the flight time ΔT (s) are calculated by the arithmetic difference of the consecutive indications obtained from the back wall of the sample which is visible on the equipment screen. The results are represented by the average of three ultrasonic readings for each sample.

$$V = 2X/\Delta t \quad (1)$$

The beam attenuation in each sample due to beam attenuation and divergence was estimated by calculating the attenuation coefficient according to Equation (2), which appears in several publications [30-33], where the attenuation coefficient α is expressed in decibels per millimeter (dB/mm). The amplitudes A_0 and A are recorded by direct reading on the equipment display and correspond to the first and second echo of the ultrasonic pulse obtained from the back wall in each sample. The experimental procedure is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Experimental procedure

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Specifically in Figure 3, the microstructural characteristics and morphology of the phases of medium carbon steel in intact condition can be seen, the ferritic structure F (light areas) – and pearlitic P (dark area), where the eutectic ferrite and cementite are structurally separated, as a result of the eutectoid transformation of austenite.

Figure 3. Microstructure of sample in intact condition (a) 50x (b) 100x

The quenching and tempering heat treatment developed on the samples produced noticeably different microstructures depending on each experimental run and in particular concerning the intact sample in the supply condition. Figure 4(a, b, c) shows the microstructural details in oil-cooled samples, where, within the grain, very thin aligned parallel strips of martensitic M are observed due to the rapid cooling rate, in addition, the acicularity increased with the austenization temperature. Figure 4(d, e, f) shows the microstructures of the tempered samples tempered at 550°C, where the martensitic structures transformed into tempered structures made up of ferrite (light areas) and cementite (dark areas). Figure 4(g, h, i) shows the microstructures in samples tempered at 650°C, visually characterized by a greater proportion of light areas (ferrite) compared to dark areas (cementite) (light) and cementite (dark). Likewise, the spheroidization of cementite is noticeable at higher tempering temperatures.

Figure 4. Microstructural details in samples austenitized at (a) 850°C, (b) 900°C, (c) 950°C; tempered at 550°C and austenitized at (d) 850°C, (e) 900°C, (f) 950°C; tempered at 650°C and austenitized at (g) 850°C; (h) 900°C; (i) 950°C

To represent the results in each sample subjected to heat treatments, three measurements of hardness, speed, and attenuation obtained from the main surface of each sample were averaged; the results are detailed in Table 2. In the research, it is observed that, in the tempered samples, where martensitic structures prevail, particularly higher hardness measurements were reported compared to those obtained in the tempered and annealed samples. In addition, a decrease in hardness is noticeable when increasing the tempering temperature. The results of the acoustic tests show the sensitivity of the measurements based on the microstructural changes induced by tempering and annealing heat treatments.

Table 2. Hardness, speed, and acoustic attenuation measurements on the samples

Tempering temperature (°C)	Tempering temperature (°C)	Speed (m/s)	Speed (m/s)	Speed (m/s)	Attenuation (dB/mm)	Attenuation (dB/m)	Attenuation (dB/m)	Hardness (Hv)	Hardness (Hv)	Hardness (Hv)
850	25	5901	5898	5899	0.2702	0.2701	0.2702	490	488	485
850	550	5922	2918	5923	0.3210	0.3205	0.3220	296	295	297
850	650	5984	5996	5999	0.3920	0.3940	0.3954	169	167	172
900	25	5876	5832	5894	0.1810	0.1812	0.1809	775	779	777
900	550	5944	5948	5944	0.2100	0.2102	0.2108	290	288	289
900	650	5974	5968	5973	0.2740	0.2760	0.2730	188	189	187
950	25	5982	5894	5891	0.1872	0.1830	0.1890	514	516	516
950	550	5926	5951	5948	0.2450	0.2453	0.2448	256	254	258
950	650	5970	5973	5975	0.3030	0.3028	0.3036	209	205	206
Sample	Intact	5908	5910	5912	0.1243	0.1247	0.1252	217.6	218.4	216.0

The tempered samples showed the lowest velocity values because the martensitic structures increase the structural volume during the austenite (FCC) to martensite (BCT) transformation, generating high dislocation density by increasing the distortion of the crystal lattice [26, 34]. In addition, the subgrain boundaries produced during the martensitic transformation disrupt the continuity of the matrix, reducing the elastic modulus and consequently, the speed of sound, as reported in [11].

In tempered samples, acoustic measurements show a tendency to increase due to the transformation of martensite into ferrite and cementite, as well as when the degree of periodization of cementite increases with increasing tempering temperature. The elastic modulus of ferritic structures is higher than that of martensitic structures, as analyzed by [33-35]. Therefore, a higher presence of ferrite compared to the content of cementite and martensite eventually implies a higher elastic modulus; of course, it also implies a faster propagation of sound.

The attenuation coefficient measurements reported the lowest values in the tempered samples, increasing in the annealed samples. The tempered martensitic structures have a higher elastic isotropy within the grain, thus, the beam scattering power decreases, as reported in [12] and [19]. In addition, martensite plates have a higher isotropy than ferrite grains [11]. The increase in the ferrite content in the tempered samples and the degree of periodization of cementite, as shown in Figure 4(g, h, i), produced greater dispersion of the ultrasonic beam.

As reported in [11] and [35], scattering increases in microstructures having larger interface areas. Furthermore, the attenuation coefficient gradually increases as the tempering temperature increases, probably due to the increased presence of ferrite from martensite transformation. The main cause of ultrasonic scattering attenuation is grain boundaries and microstructural interfaces as reported by [12] and [25].

It should be noted that the morphological change produced in the sample quenched and tempered at 900 and 650°C, modified the properties of the study to a greater extent concerning its initial condition. As detailed in Table 3, the hardness experienced a reduction of 75.74%, and the speed and attenuation of the beam increased by 1.78% and 51.5% respectively.

Table 3. Percentage of losses and increases in acoustic parameters due to quenching and tempering

Tempering temperature (°C)	Hardness Tempered at 550 °C (%)	Hardness Tempered at 650 °C (%)	Tempering Rate at 550 °C (%)	Tempering Rate at 650 °C (%)	Tempering Attenuation at 550 °C (%)	Tempering Attenuation at 650 °C (%)
850	-39,418	-65,417	+0.367	+1,588	+18,789	+45,647
900	-62,758	-75.74	+1,329	+1,778	+13,236	+51,484
950	-50,368	-59,869	+0.326	+0.85	+30.84	+61,855

Note. (+) increase, (-) decrease

Eventually, it is important to correlate the acoustic properties with the resistance of the material based on the microstructural changes due to the effect of each thermal cycle imposed during the heat treatments, which is why the experimental data were arranged in a contour graph, as shown in Figure 5. Where it is

possible to infer that the acoustic properties present a negative correlation with the hardness measurements. The attenuation coefficient and the speed of the sonic beam decrease as the hardness of the material increases.

Figure 5. Correlation between acoustic properties and hardness

4. CONCLUSIONS

The heat treatments of quenching and tempering have produced noticeably different microstructures depending on the thermal cycle imposed. The acoustic properties and the resistance to indentation of the material show sensitivity to vary significantly depending on the microstructural changes induced in the samples.

This fact has allowed obtaining a correlation of properties in a contour graph.

There is a negative correlation between the acoustic properties and the hardness reported in the samples. The attenuation coefficient and the ultrasonic beam velocity with the lowest values are reported in samples with higher hardness due to the presence of martensitic structures.

After tempering, there is a softening in the samples because the transformation of martensite into phases consisting of ferrite and cementite occurs, which explains the increase in the acoustic properties in these samples.

REFERENCES

- [1] Palanichamy P. et al. (1995). Ultrasonic velocity measurements for estimation of grain size in austenitic stainless steel. *NDT & E International* 28(3), 179-185.
- [2] Generazio E. (1984). The role of the reflection coefficient in precision measurement of ultrasonic attenuation. En *Annual Review of Progress in Quantitative Nondestructive Evaluation*. LaJolla, California.
- [3] American Society for Testing and Materials. (2020). ASTM E 494-20: Standard Practice for Measuring Ultrasonic Velocity in Materials. ASTM.
- [4] Uzun F. y Bilge, A. (2015). Application of ultrasonic waves in measurement of hardness of welded carbon steels. *Def. Technol.* 11(3), 255-261.
- [5] Rojas E. et al. (2024). Integration of Experimental Methods for the Correlation of Hardness with the Propagation Velocity of Ultrasonic Signals in Steel: A Proposal for an Undergraduate Material Science Lecture. *Experimental Techniques* 48, 559-567.
- [6] Toozandehjani M. et al. (2015). On the correlation between microstructural evolution and ultrasonic properties: a review. *J. Mater. Sci.* 50, 2643-2665.
- [7] Rodríguez E. et al. (2011). Characterization of microstructural changes in a duplex stainless steel using spectral analysis and conventional ultrasonic techniques. *Mater. Test.* 53(9), 564-571.
- [8] Khan S. et al. (2016). Evaluation of the properties of AISI 316L stainless steel materials by means of non-destructive tests. *Nondestructive testing and Evaluation* 31(4), 360-370.
- [9] Choi S. et al. (2019). Comparison of Linear and Nonlinear Ultrasonic Parameters in Characterizing Grain Size and Mechanical Properties of 304L Stainless Steel. *Metals* 9(12), 1279.
- [10] Tehrani N. et al. (2019). Metallurgical Characterization of a Low Carbon Steel Microstructure Using Linear and Nonlinear Ultrasonics. *J. Mater. Eng. Perform.* 28, 7206-7212.
- [11] Hakan C. y Keleş Y. (2003). Ultrasonic characterisation of hot-rolled and heat-treated plain carbon steels. *Insight - Non-Destructive Testing and Condition Monitoring* 45, 615-620.
- [12] Papadakis E. (1970). Ultrasonic attenuation and velocity in SAE 52100 steel quenched from various temperatures. *Metall. Trans.* 1, 1053-1057.
- [13] El-Rayes M. et al. (2015). Ultrasonic characterization of heat-treatment effects on SAE-1040 and 4340 steels. *J. Mater. Process. Technol.* 216, 188-198.
- [14] Murav'ev V. et al. (2019). Acoustoelasticity investigation of the biaxial stress state in R65 rails. *Intellekt. Sistemy Proizv* 17(1), 19-25.
- [15] Murav'eva O. et al. (2020). Sensitivity of Electromagnetic-Acoustic Multiple Shadow Method Using Rayleigh Waves in Inspection of Oil Country Tubular Goods. *Russ. J. Nondestruct. Test.* 56, 995-1004.
- [16] Aleshin N. et al. (2017). On the Possibility of Using Ultrasonic Surface and Head Waves in Nondestructive Quality Checks of Additive Manufactured Products. *Russ. J. Nondestruct. Test.* 53, 830-838.
- [17] Murav'eva O. y Murav'ev V. (2016). Methodological peculiarities of using SH- and Lamb waves when assessing the anisotropy of properties of flats. *Russ. J. Nondestruct. Test.* 52, 363-36.
- [18] Murav'eva O. et al. (2022). Acoustic properties of low-carbon 2% Mn-doped steel manufactured by laser powder bed fusion technology. *Addit. Manuf.* 51, 102635.
- [19] Kumar A., et al. (2002). Comprehensive microstructural characterization in modified 9Cr-1Mo ferritic steel by ultrasonic measurements. *Metall. Mater. Trans. A.* 33, 1617-1626.
- [20] Li W. et al. (2019). Characterization of Microstructural Evolution by Ultrasonic Nonlinear Parameters Adjusted by Attenuation Factor. *Metals* 9(3), 271.
- [21] Arnold W. et al. (2023). Ultrasonic Non-destructive Materials Characterization. En *Non-destructive Materials Characterization and Evaluation*. Springer Series in Materials Science vol. 329.
- [22] Botvina L. et al. (2000). A new method for assessing the mean grain size of polycrystalline materials using ultrasonic NDE. *J. Mater. Sci.* 35, 4673-4683.
- [23] Liu Y. et al. (2021). Grain Size Estimation using phased array ultrasound attenuation. *NDT & E International* 122, 102479.
- [24] Wan T. et al. (2017). Effects of Grain Size on Ultrasonic Attenuation in Type 316L Stainless Steel. *Materials* 10(7), 753.
- [25] Aghaie-Khafri M. et al. (2012). Characterization of grain size and yield strength in AISI 301 stainless steel by ultrasonic attenuation measurements. *Journal of Nondestructive Evaluation* 31, 191-196.
- [26] Hakan C. y Orkun B. (2005). Characterization of microstructural phases of steels by sound velocity measurement. *Mater. Charact.* 55(2), 160-166.
- [27] Avner S. (1997). *Introduction to Physical Metallurgy*. Second edition. MC GRAW HILL.
- [28] Krauss G. (2005). *Steels: Heat Treatment and Processing Principles*. ASM International.
- [29] Dossett J. (2020). *Practical Heat Treating: Basic Principles*. ASM International.
- [30] Vijayalakshmi K. et al. (2011). Influence of heat treatment on the microstructure, ultrasonic attenuation and hardness of SAF 2205 duplex stainless steel. *Mater. Sci. Eng. A* 529, 447-451.

- [31] Vera J. et al. (2023). Parámetros Acústicos en Estándares de Referencia para Calibración del Sistema de Prueba de Ultrasonido Industrial. En 21st LACCEI International Multi-Conference for Engineering, Education, and Technology. Buenos Aires, Argentina.
- [32] Stella J. et al. (2009). Characterization of the sensitization degree in the AISI 304 stainless steel using spectral analysis and conventional ultrasonic techniques. *NDT & E International* 42, 267–274.
- [33] Freitas V. et al. (2011). Nondestructive characterization and evaluation of embrittlement kinetics and elastic constants of duplex stainless steel SAF2205 for different aging times at 425°C and 475°C. *J. Nondestruct. Eval.* 30, 130–136.
- [34] Hakan C. y Cam I. (2007). Comparison of magnetic Barkhausen noise and ultrasonic velocity measurements for microstructure evaluation of SAE 1040 and SAE 4140 steels. *Mater. Charact.* 58(5), 447-454.
- [35] Hakan C. y Tuncer B. (2004). Investigating the microstructure-ultrasonic property relationships in steels. En 16th World Conference on NDT. Montreal, Canadá.